

Novel bacterial strains, suitable for use in large-scale fermentation, for the maintenance and replication of Petit Plasmid.

Author: **Rojopitiavana Solofondrazaintsoanirina***

*Correspondence: solofo.rojo@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10517661, published online: January 16, 2024

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	2
Design	2
Implementation.....	7
References.....	9
Supplementary materials	11

Disclaimer

The information provided in this document is intended for educational and informational purposes only. The author and publisher of this document are not responsible for any consequences that may arise from the use, misuse, or application of the techniques, methods, or instructions described herein. Instructions and guidelines outlined in this document are based on the author's understanding and knowledge as of the publication date. Scientific knowledge and technologies are constantly evolving, and readers are advised to consult with appropriate experts and references before conducting any experiments described in this document. Mention of specific trademarks or registered trademarks in this document does not imply endorsement, affiliation, or association with their holders. Trademarks belong to their respective owners and are used for identification purposes only. Readers should exercise caution and judgment when applying the information provided in this document. The author and publisher do not assume any responsibility for errors, omissions, or inaccuracies that may be present in the content. Additionally, readers are advised to comply with all applicable laws, regulations, and ethical considerations related to scientific experiments, inventions, and intellectual property. By using this document, readers acknowledge that they do so at their own risk and agree to hold the author and publisher harmless from any liability, claims, or damages that may arise from the use of the information provided herein.

Introduction

I previously introduced a class of antibiotic-free small DNA vectors termed “Petit Plasmids” [1]. These vectors can be maintained and replicated within engineered amino acid auxotrophic bacterial strains cultivated in a medium lacking one or more essential amino acids. In large-scale fermentation systems, these growing cells can scavenge lysed cells to obtain the essential amino acids, promoting the survival of cells lacking Petit Plasmid. To address this limitation, I present novel strains of engineered bacterial cells that require a specific inducing agent for growth in the absence of Petit Plasmid.

In the initial design [1], a “gene of interest” that might correspond to *Escherichia coli*'s *argA*, *hisB*, *ilvA*, *leuB*, *lysA*, *metA*, *proA*, *pheA*, *thrC*, *trpC*, or *tyrA*, is knocked-out or deleted, rendering resulting bacterial strain auxotrophic for the corresponding amino acid (L-arginine, L-Histidine, L-Isoleucine, L-Leucine, L-Lysine, L-Methionine, L-Proline, L-Phenylalanine, L-Threonine, L-Tryptophan, or tyrosine, respectively). A DNA sequence comprising the same “gene of interest”, under the control of an RNA switch, is integrated into the cell's genome to create engineered amino acid auxotrophic strains capable of supporting the maintenance and replication of “Petit Plasmid”. In this disclosure, the choice of “gene of interest” is expanded to encompass any essential genes whose knockout or deletion would inhibit cell growth and/or result in cell death.

Expression of a first “gene of interest” is switched-on in the presence of “activating RNAs” encoded on Petit Plasmid. In the absence of the latter, the survival of the engineered cells can be ensured by providing an inducible transgene that expresses either:

- Activating RNAs when the medium is supplemented with an inducer, or
- The same “gene of interest” when the medium is supplemented with an inducer.

In both scenarios, the first “gene of interest” is expressed in the presence of an inducer, ensuring cell survival in the absence of Petit Plasmid.

Design

As previously explained [1], Petit Plasmid comprises a STAR cassette, serving as a selectable marker, and an origin of replication sequence, essential for the plasmid's maintenance and replication within a suitable bacterial host. A STAR cassette comprises a promoter, a STAR-encoding sequence (or an activating RNA CDS), and a terminator. An exemplary linear Petit Plasmid, further comprising a multiple cloning site (MCS), is depicted in FIGURE 1. An exemplary linear transposon Petit Plasmid is shown in FIGURE 2. A circular plasmid can be obtained by covalently linking the 5' end with the 3' end.

FIGURE 1: An exemplary sequence architecture of Petit Plasmid.

FIGURE 2: An exemplary sequence architecture of a transposon Petit Plasmid.

A previously disclosed DNA cassette, denoted as "Activating RNA-Inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGoI), is illustrated in FIGURE 3 (see ref [1]). The first novel ARIGoI architecture, disclosed herein, is depicted in FIGURE 4. The Gene of Interest (GoI) can be a drug-resistance gene, encoding a naturally occurring or a recombinant polypeptide such as Aminoglycoside 3'-phosphotransferase (KanR), Bleomycin resistance protein (BleoR), Hygromycin-B 4-O-kinase (HygR), Puromycin N-acetyltransferase (PuroR), and *E. coli* L28R dihydrofolate reductase [2], which confer resistance against Kanamycin, Bleomycin, Hygromycin, Puromycin, and trimethoprim respectively. A replication gene that encodes a replication polypeptide such as π or parA proteins can be further inserted 5' of the RNA switch sequence (FIGURE 5).

FIGURE 3: Architecture of a previously disclosed "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGoI).

FIGURE 4: Architecture of the first newly disclosed "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGoI). Reading is always from 5' to 3'. Promoter 2 and 3 are preferably constitutive. The recombinase binding sites are both in the forward or reverse orientation. The 5' and 3' homologous arms are sequences that permit the targeted integration of ARIGoI into any desired location in the host genome. Promoter 3, its RBS, and antibiotic resistance gene can be replaced with a STAR cassette.

FIGURE 5: Architecture of the first newly disclosed "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGoI) wherein a replication gene can be joint-transcribed with the "gene of interest"

The second novel ARIGol architecture is depicted in FIGURE 6. It comprises “two gene of interest” (Gol) encoding the same essential polypeptide. Of course, the polypeptides can be different but they should both perform the same function. The first Gol is under the control of an inducible promoter, activatable by an inducer. The second Gol is under the control of an RNA switch sequence, activated in the presence of activating RNAs. Preferably, Promoter 2 is constitutive and devoid of a Ribosome Binding Site (RBS). Both Gols can be individually codon-optimized to minimize the likelihood of homologous recombination. The antibiotic resistance gene facilitates the selection of cells transformed with ARIGol, and subsequent removal can be achieved through site-specific recombinase-mediated excision (FIGURE 7).

A Gene of Interest (Gol) encodes an essential polypeptide. Inhibition, deletion, or knock-out of the corresponding gene on the bacterial genome impedes growth and/or results in lethality. Exemplary candidates are disclosed in [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], WO2023166132A1. An inducible promoter one that is repressed in the absence or presence of an inducer. Inducible promoters suitable for use in the present disclosure are preferably repressed in the absence of an inducer. They include the arabinose-inducible araBAD promoter [10], anhydrotetracycline-inducible tetR promoter [11], crystal violet-inducible promoter [12], rhamnose-inducible promoter [13], galactose-inducible promoter [14], lactose-inducible promoter [15], and the uric acid-inducible promoter [16].

FIGURE 6: Architecture of the second newly disclosed "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGol). Promoter 1 is preferably inducible and inactive in the absence of a suitable inducer. The first and second Gene of Interests (Gols) encode the same essential polypeptide. Promoter 2 and 3 are preferably constitutive. The terminators, ribosome binding sites, and Gol can have different sequences so to minimize homologous recombination. The recombinase binding sites are both in the forward or reverse orientation. DNA sequence(s), transgene(s) or cassette(s) necessary for the proper functioning of inducible promoter 1 can be inserted 3' of the 5' homologous arm and 5' of promoter 1. The 5' and 3' homologous arms are sequences that permit the targeted integration of ARIGol into any desired location in the host genome.

FIGURE 7: Architecture of a chromosomally integrated ARIGol after site-specific recombinase-mediated excision of its antibiotic resistance cassette.

In the second newly disclosed ARIGol, the first Gol, regulated by inducible promoter 1, can be substituted with an activating RNA coding sequence, and its RBS can be removed (FIGURE 8). Promoter 1 can be constitutive, and its associated ribosome binding site can be replaced with a theophylline-inducible

riboswitch [17] or a temperature-responsive transcriptional regulator from *L. monocytogenes* [18], controlling the expression of the first Gol with theophylline or temperature, respectively.

FIGURE 8: Architecture of the second newly disclosed "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGol) wherein the first RBS is removed and its first "gene of interest" is replaced with an activating RNA coding sequence.

A replication gene encoding a replication polypeptide such as π or parA can be inserted 5' of the RNA switch sequence (FIGURE 9). A ribosome binding site and a SacB gene can be further inserted 3' of the first Gol (FIGURE 10) or the activating RNA CDS. Upon the addition of sucrose to the growth medium, any cells whose first Gol (or activating RNA CDS) is not tightly repressed in the absence of an inducer will be eliminated. Subsequent to the step of positive selection, the antibiotic resistance gene of ARIGol can be excised via site-specific recombinase-mediated excision (FIGURE 11).

FIGURE 9: An "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGol) wherein a replication gene can be joint-transcribed with the second "gene of interest".

FIGURE 10: Architecture of a newly disclosed "Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest" (ARIGol) wherein a SacB gene is joint-transcribed with the first "gene of interest", and a replication gene can be joint-transcribed with the second "gene of interest". Promoter 1 is inducible, and promoter 2 and 3 are preferably constitutive. The first ribosome binding site and the first gene of interest can be replaced with an activating RNA CDS.

FIGURE 11: Architecture of a chromosomally integrated ARIGol wherein a *SacB* gene is joint-transcribed with the first “gene of interest”, a replication gene is joint-transcribed with the second “gene of interest”, and the antibiotic resistance cassette is excised. One or more insulators and/or terminator sequences can be inserted 3’ of the 5’ homologous arm and 5’ of promoter 1 to further minimize possible leakage resulting from transcriptional read-through.

During the genomic integration step, ARIGol can be integrated in a safe harbor site or used to disrupt the desired essential gene for deletion or knockout. In the latter case, the cell can recover in a medium supplemented with an inducer to enable proper expression of the now essential first GOI. The DNA sequences of the two GOI on the ARIGol can be codon-optimized to minimize homologous recombination with each other or with the essential gene on the cell's genome.

A bacterial strain deleted or knocked-out of an essential gene, comprising an integrated ARIGol, and lacking Petit Plasmid, cannot survive without supplementation of the culture medium with an appropriate inducer (FIGURE 12). Following bacterial transformation with Petit Plasmids, transformants are selected by culturing cells on appropriate agar plates or media lacking the inducer. Seed cultures can be started by streaking colonies on minimal agar plates lacking the inducer. After incubation at 30-37°C for 11-18h, well-isolated and colony PCR-verified colonies are inoculated into media lacking the inducer, providing 0.01-1% inocula for use in laboratory-scale or large-scale fermentation. Media used for culture or fermentation should lack the inducer or should not be supplemented with the inducer if initially present. Plasmids are extracted and purified using commercially-available kits or methods well known in the art [19].

FIGURE 12: Effects of the presence or absence of Petit Plasmid and “inducer” on bacterial growth. The terms “Gol is expressed” and “Gol is repressed” concern the gene of interest located 3’ of the RNA switch. The first gene of interest and its RBS can be replaced with an activating RNA coding sequence.

Implementation

Exemplary DNA sequence of promoters, terminators, ribosome binding sites, STAR cassettes, the polypeptide sequence of SacB, KanR, π protein, and the sequence architecture of various Petit Plasmids are already disclosed in ref [1]. Additional sequences are presented in Table S1 and Table S2.

Described herein is a method of engineering an enhanced *Escherichia coli* strain knocked-out for the gene *infA* that encodes Translation initiation factor IF-1 polypeptide [20], and comprising a genomically integrated ARGol sequence. The latter is named “cassette ARGol_pir_infA” and comprises: a 126-nt left homologous arm taken from the 5' region of *infA* gene, a terminator sequence, an araBAD cassette, an *E. coli* codon-optimized gene of interest (Gol) encoding the IF-1 polypeptide, an RBS, an *E. coli* codon-optimized SacB gene, a terminator, a constitutive promoter with a RBS, a replication gene encoding π polypeptide, an RNA switch sequence also called dual transcription-translation activator, an *E. coli* codon-optimized gene of interest (Gol) encoding the IF-1 polypeptide, a terminator, an Flp recombinase binding site, a constitutive promoter with an RBS, an KanR antibiotic resistance gene, a Flp recombinase binding site, a terminator, and an 100-nt right homologous arm taken from the 3' region of *infA* gene.

The cassette ARGol_pir_infA is PCR-amplified with the following primers (designed from the sequence CP011113.2, genbank):

- Forward: 5'-CCTATCGTTTATCTCACCGCTCCCTTATAC-3'
- Reverse: 5'-CTCGTTCTTTCTCTTCGCCCATCAG-3'

PCR products are run on agarose gel, then the band of the correct size is cut-out and processed using an appropriate gel extraction kit by following instructor's manual.

Some examples of suitable *E. coli* strains, their preparation and uses are already disclosed in ref [1]. The amounts of antibiotics added to culture media are: kanamycin (50 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), ampicillin (100 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), and chloramphenicol (34 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). The concentration of L-arabinose for supplementation is 0.25-1% (w/v).

pKD46 is a temperature-sensitive plasmid that encodes an arabinose-inducible lambda red recombination system. It is transfected into a selected strain by chemical transformation or electroporation. Successful recombinants are selected on plates with ampicillin at a temperature between 30-32 °C. After overnight growth, 5-20 colonies are inoculated into LB (Luria Bertani) medium with ampicillin and screened by colony PCR to identify transformants harboring the pKD46-encoded lambda red recombination system. Media containing positive colonies are grown to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.2 at 30°C. 0.25-1% (w/v) of L-arabinose is added to the media, and the culture is grown at 30°C until the OD₆₀₀ reaches 0.4-0.6. Before performing electroporation, the cells should be washed with ice-cold deionized water 2-3 times by repeated pelleting (by centrifugation) and resuspension. After the last pelleting, cells are resuspended in 10% glycerol.

The gel-purified linear ARGol_pir_infA is electroporated or chemically transformed into the cells. Use between 30-150 μl of the cell culture and add a volume containing 2-5 μl of ARGol_pir_infA DNA. After transformation, immediately pour the suspension into 1-2 mL of LB (Luria Bertani) medium containing 0.25-1% (w/v) of L-arabinose and allow the cells to recover by incubating at 37°C for 1 hour. Spread the bacterial culture on LB plates with L-arabinose and kanamycin and incubate overnight at 37°C. Pick 5-20 colonies, inoculate into LB medium with L-arabinose and kanamycin, and screen by colony PCR to identify and confirm transformants harboring the chromosomally integrated ARGol_pir_infA. The following primers are used for PCR-amplification (designed from the sequence CP011113.2, genbank):

- Forward: 5'-CCTATCGTTTATCTCACCGCTCCCTTATAC-3'
- Reverse: 5'-CTCGTTCCTTCTCTTCGCCCATCAG-3'

Bands of the correct size are gel-purified and sent for sequencing. Positive transformants will be transformed with the plasmid pCP20 to remove the KanR gene.

pCP20 is a temperature-sensitive plasmid that encodes a temperature-inducible Flp recombinase. It is transformed into the cells by chemical transformation or electroporation. After transformation, immediately pour the suspension into 1-2 mL of LB medium + L-arabinose and allow the cells to recover by incubating at 30°C for 1 hour. Spread the bacterial culture on LB plates with L-arabinose and chloramphenicol and incubate overnight at 30°C. Pick 5-20 colonies, inoculate into LB medium with 6% sucrose (w/v), 0.25-1% L-arabinose (w/v) and incubate overnight at 42-43°C.

Prepare 10^4 - 10^6 dilutions of the overnight culture and plate 50 μ L of the dilutions on LB plates + L-arabinose. Incubate overnight at 30°C. Select randomly 5-20 colonies and patch on LB + chloramphenicol + L-arabinose, LB + kanamycin + L-arabinose, LB + ampicillin + L-arabinose, LB + L-arabinose, and LB. Inoculate the colonies in 5 mL of LB + L-arabinose medium. Incubate the plates and media at 37°C overnight. Select for colonies that are kanamycin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin sensitive, and that show growth on LB plates + L-arabinose but not in LB plates. PCR-verify the colonies to check for successful elimination of the KanR sequence.

Bands of the correct size are gel-purified and sent for sequencing. The resulting strain should be maintained in medium supplemented with L-arabinose and capable of maintaining and replicating a Petit Plasmid harboring a minimal R6Ky origin of replication.

An engineered *Escherichia coli* strain is called *E. coli* Δ infA:: $[\pi$ -arac^{ind}(infA)-dtta^{ind}(infA)]. π : the strain constitutively expresses π protein. arac^{ind}(infA): the gene that encodes IF-1 is under the control of araBAD promoter. dtta^{ind}(infA): the gene that encodes IF-1 is under the control of a small transcription activating RNAs (STAR)-**inducible** **du**al **tr**anscription-**tr**anslation activator sequence. Examples of strains are *E. coli* Stb13[®] Δ infA:: $[\pi$ -arac^{ind}(infA)-dtta^{ind}(infA)] and *E. coli* DH10B Δ infA:: $[\pi$ -arac^{ind}(infA)-dtta^{ind}(infA)].

The engineered strains are cultured on agar plates or in media supplemented with L-arabinose for their maintenance. Before transformation, cells are preferably rendered competent. After their transformation with Petit Plasmid, cells can be cultured in 1-5 mL culture medium lacking or containing L-arabinose at 30°C for 30 minutes to 1 hour to allow recovery. The culture can be spread on LB agar plates without L-arabinose and incubated at 30-37°C for 18-24 h to select for transformants. Positive colonies identified by colony-PCR can be cultured in nutrient-rich medium without L-arabinose. 5-50 mL of culture medium can be used for standard molecular biology applications. Plasmids can be extracted and purified with commercially-available Miniprep kits by following the vendor's instructions.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of interest statement

The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Solofondrazaintsoanirina, Rojopitiavana, “Petit Plasmid: A Small, Versatile Antibiotic-Free Multi-Application DNA Vector Driving Biotech Innovation” (Zenodo, 2023).
- [2] H. Abdizadeh, Y. T. Tamer, O. Acar, E. Toprak, A. R. Atilgan, and C. Atilgan, “Increased substrate affinity in the *Escherichia coli* L28R dihydrofolate reductase mutant causes trimethoprim resistance,” *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **19**, 11416–11428 (2017).
- [3] K. Kobayashi, S. D. Ehrlich, A. Albertini, G. Amati, K. K. Andersen, M. Arnaud, K. Asai, S. Ashikaga, S. Aymerich, et al., “Essential *Bacillus subtilis* genes,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **100**, 4678–4683 (2003).
- [4] T. C. Umland, L. W. Schultz, U. MacDonald, J. M. Beanan, R. Olson, and T. A. Russo, “*In Vivo* - Validated Essential Genes Identified in *Acinetobacter baumannii* by Using Human Ascites Overlap Poorly with Essential Genes Detected on Laboratory Media,” *mBio* **3**, G. L. Drusano, Ed., e00113-12 (2012).
- [5] E. C. A. Goodall, A. Robinson, I. G. Johnston, S. Jabbari, K. A. Turner, A. F. Cunningham, P. A. Lund, J. A. Cole, and I. R. Henderson, “The Essential Genome of *Escherichia coli* K-12,” *mBio* **9**, e02096-17 (2018).
- [6] C. Martelli, A. De Martino, E. Marinari, M. Marsili, and I. Pérez Castillo, “Identifying essential genes in *Escherichia coli* from a metabolic optimization principle,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **106**, 2607–2611 (2009).
- [7] S. Billerbeck and S. Panke, “A genetic replacement system for selection-based engineering of essential proteins,” *Microb Cell Fact* **11**, 110 (2012).
- [8] R. Liang and J. Liu, “In-frame deletion of *Escherichia coli* essential genes in complex regulon,” *BioTechniques* **44**, 209–215 (2008).
- [9] T. Bergmiller, M. Ackermann, and O. K. Silander, “Patterns of Evolutionary Conservation of Essential Genes Correlate with Their Compensability,” *PLoS Genet* **8**, I. Matic, Ed., e1002803 (2012).
- [10] A. Khlebnikov, T. Skaug, and J. D. Keasling, “Modulation of gene expression from the arabinose-inducible araBAD promoter,” *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol* **29**, 34–37 (2002).
- [11] H. Dong, W. Tao, Y. Zhang, and Y. Li, “Development of an anhydrotetracycline-inducible gene expression system for solvent-producing *Clostridium acetobutylicum*: A useful tool for strain engineering,” *Metab Eng* **14**, 59–67 (2012).
- [12] T. L. Ruegg, J. H. Pereira, J. C. Chen, A. DeGiovanni, P. Novichkov, V. K. Mutalik, G. P. Tomaleri, S. W. Singer, N. J. Hillson, et al., “Jungle Express is a versatile repressor system for tight transcriptional control,” *Nat Commun* **9**, 3617 (2018).
- [13] S. T. Cardona and M. A. Valvano, “An expression vector containing a rhamnose-inducible promoter provides tightly regulated gene expression in *Burkholderia cenocepacia*,” *Plasmid* **54**, 219–228 (2005).
- [14] H. G. Menzella and H. C. Gramajo, “Recombinant protein production in high cell density cultures of *Escherichia coli* with galactose as a gratuitous inducer,” *Biotechnol Prog* **20**, 1263–1266 (2004).
- [15] A. K. Gombert and B. V. Kilikian, “Recombinant gene expression in *Escherichia coli* cultivation using lactose as inducer,” *J Biotechnol* **60**, 47–54 (1998).
- [16] C. Liang, D. Xiong, Y. Zhang, S. Mu, and S.-Y. Tang, “Development of a novel uric-acid-responsive regulatory system in *Escherichia coli*,” *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* **99**, 2267–2275 (2015).
- [17] S. Topp, C. M. K. Reynoso, J. C. Seeliger, I. S. Goldlust, S. K. Desai, D. Murat, A. Shen, A. W. Puri, A. Komeili, et al., “Synthetic Riboswitches That Induce Gene Expression in Diverse Bacterial Species,” *Appl Environ Microbiol* **76**, 7881–7884 (2010).

- [18] P. P. Pagni, J. Chaplin, M. Wijaranakula, J. D. Wesley, J. Granger, J. Cracraft, C. O'Brien, N. Perdue, V. Kumar, et al., "Multicomponent Plasmid Protects Mice From Spontaneous Autoimmune Diabetes," *Diabetes* **71**, 157–169 (2022).
- [19] J. Stadler, R. Lemmens, and T. Nyhammar, "Plasmid DNA purification," *J. Gene Med.* **6**, S54–S66 (2004).
- [20] H. S. Cummings and J. W. Hershey, "Translation initiation factor IF1 is essential for cell viability in *Escherichia coli*," *J Bacteriol* **176**, 198–205 (1994).

Supplementary materials

Table S1: DNA sequence of exemplary parts

Name	Description	Sequence
5'_HA_infA	5' homologous arm derived from the 5' region of <i>E. coli</i> infA gene.	CCTATCGTTTATCTCACCGCTCCCTTATACGTTGCGCTTTTGG TGCGGCTTAGCCGTGTGTTTTCGGAGTAATGTGCCGAACCT GTTTGTTGCGATTTAGCGCGCAAATCTTACTTATTTACAGA
3'_HA_infA	3' homologous arm derived from the 3' region of <i>E. coli</i> infA gene.	GTGACTGTTGAACTGACCCCGTACGACCTGAGCAAAGGCCG CATTGTCTCCGTAGTCGCTGATTGTTTTACCGCTGATGGG CGAAGAGAAAAGAACGAG
infA_seq_1	Sequence encoding <i>E. coli</i> Translation initiation factor IF-1	ATGGCTAAAGAAGATAACATTGAAATGCAAGGACTGTGTT GGAAACTCTGCCAAATACTATGTTTCGTGTTGAATTAGAGA ATGGTCACGTTGTGACTGCACATATTTCTGGTAAGATGAGA AAGAACTATATCAGGATCTTGACTGGTGACAAAGTTACCGT TGAATTGACTCCATATGATTTAAGCAAGGGTAGGATTGTGT TTCGTTCTCGCTGA
infA_seq_2	Sequence encoding <i>E. coli</i> Translation initiation factor IF-1	ATGGCGAAAGAGGACAACATCGAGATGCAAGGCACCGTGC TGGAAACCCTGCCGAACACCATGTTTCGCGTGGAAGTGGAG AACGGCCATGTGGTGACCGCGCATATTAGCGGCAAGATGC GCAAGAACTATATCCGCATTCTGACCGGCGACAAGGTGACC GTGGAGCTGACGCCGTATGATCTGAGCAAAGGCCGATTGT GTTTCGAGCCGCTAA
araBAD	araC (reversed); araBAD promoter; Ribosome binding site	CACATTTCCCCGAAAAGTGCCACCTGCATCGATTTATATATGA CAACTTGACGGCTACATCATTCACTTTTTCTTACAACCGGC ACGGAACTCGCTCGGGCTGGCCCCGGTGCATTTTTAAATA CCCGCGAGAAATAGAGTTGATCGTCAAACCAACATTGCGA CCGACGGTGGCGATAGGCATCCGGGTGGTGCTCAAAGCA GCTTCGCTGGCTGATACGTTGGTCTCGCGCCAGCTTAAG ACGCTAATCCCTAACTGCTGGCGAAAAGATGTGACAGACG CGACGGCGACAAGCAAACATGCTGTGCGACGCTGGCGATA TCAAATTGCTGTCTGCCAGGTGATCGCTGATGTACTGACA AGCCTCGGTACCCGATTATCCATCGGTGGATGGAGCGACT CGTTAATCGCTTCCATGCGCCGAGTAACAATTGCTCAAGCA GATTTATCGCCAGCAGCTCCGAATAGCGCCCTCCCTTGCC CGCGTTAATGATTTGCCAAACAGGTGCTGAAATGCGGC TGGTGCCTTTCATCCGGGCGAAAAGAACCCCGTATTGGCAA TATTGACGGCCAGTTAAGCCATTCATGCCAGTAGGCGCGCG GACGAAAGTAAACCCACTGGTGATACCATTGCGAGCCTCC GGATGACGACCGTAGTGATGAATCTCTCTGGCGGGAACA GCAAAATATCACCCGGTCGGCAAACAAATCTCGTCCCTGA TTTTTACCACCCCTGACCGCGAATGGTGAGATTGAGAAT ATAACCTTTCATTTCCAGCGGTGCGTGCATAAAAAAATCGA GATAACCGTTGGCCTCAATCGGCGTTAAACCCGCCACCAGA TGGCATTAAACGAGTATCCCGGCAGCAGGGGATCATTTTG CGCTTCAGCCATACTTTTCATACTCCCGCATTAGAGAAGA AACCAATTGTCCATATTGCATCAGACATTGCCGTCCTGCGT CTTTACTGGCTCTTCTCGTAACCAAACCGGTAACCCCGCT TATTAAGCATTCTGTAACAAAGCGGGACC AAAGCCATGA CAAAACGCGTAACAAAAGTGCTATAATCACGGCAGAAAA

		GTCCACATTGATTATTTGCACGGCGTCACACTTTGCTATGCC ATAGCATTTTTATCCATAAGATTAGCGGATCCTACCTGACGC TTTTTATCGCAACTCTACTGTTTCTCCATACCCGTTTTTTTG GGAATTCGAGCTCTAAGGAGGTTATAAAAA
bleoR_seq	Bleomycin resistance protein	ATGGCCAAGTTGACCAAGTGCCGTTCCGGTGCTCACCCGCGG CGACGTCGCCGGAGCGGTTCGAGTTCTGGACCGACCGGCTC GGTTCTCCCGGACTTCGTGGAGGACGACTTCGCCGGTGT GGTCCGGGACGACGTGACCCTGTTTCATCAGCGCGGTCCAG GACCAGGTGGTGCCGACAACACCCTGGCCTGGGTGTGGG TGC GCGGCCTGGACGAGCTGTACGCCGAGTGGTCCGGAGGT CGTGTCCACGAACTTCCGGGACGCCTCCGGGCCGGCCATGA CCGAGATCGGCGAGCAGCCGTGGGGGCGGGAGTTCGCCCT GCGGACCCGGCCGCAACTGCGTGCACTTCGTGGCCGAG GAGCAGGACTGA

Table S2: Sequence architectures of exemplary Activating RNA-inducible Gene of Interest (ARIGol).

Name	Description	Sequence architecture (5' -> 3')
ARIGol_pir_infA	FIGURE 10	5'_HA_infA; araBAD; infA_seq_1; RBS_rhaS_20k; SaB_seq; Term_BB a_B1005; Prom_BB a_J23108; RBS_1; Pir_seq; Tta2_pT181; infA_seq_2; Term_T7; Rec_frt_wt; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; 3'_HA_infA
ARIGol_pir_infA_2	FIGURE 9	5'_HA_infA; araBAD; infA_seq_1; Term_BB a_B1005; Prom_BB a_J23108; RBS_1; Pir_seq; Tta2_pT181; infA_seq_2; Term_T7; Rec_frt_wt; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; 3'_HA_infA
ARIGol_infA_1	FIGURE 8	5'_HA_infA; araBAD (no RBS); STAR_1; Term_T500; Prom_BB a_J23108; Tta2_pT181; infA_seq_2; Term_T7; Rec_frt_wt; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; 3'_HA_infA
ARIGol_infA_2	FIGURE 6	5'_HA_infA; araBAD; infA_seq_1; Term_BB a_B1005; Prom_BB a_J23108; Tta2_pT181; infA_seq_2; Term_T7; Rec_frt_wt; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; 3'_HA_infA
ARIGol_pir_infA_3	FIGURE 5	5'_HA_infA; Prom_BB a_J23108; RBS_1; Pir_seq; Tta2_pT181; bleoR_seq; Term_T7; Rec_frt_wt; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; 3'_HA_infA
ARIGol_pir_infA_4	FIGURE 4	5'_HA_infA; Prom_BB a_J23108; Tta2_pT181; bleoR_seq; Term_T7; Rec_frt_wt; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; 3'_HA_infA